

ARTICLE

The Influence of Product Completeness, Outlet Atmosphere, Service Quality, and Price Perception on Purchasing Decisions at Kimia Farma Pharmacy, Sam Ratulangi Manado

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the effect of product completeness, outlet atmosphere, service quality, and price perception on purchasing decisions at Kimia Farma Sam Ratulangi Manado Pharmacy, both simultaneously and partially. This study uses a descriptive approach with a quantitative method, without comparing or connecting independent variables with other variables. Data were collected through questionnaires distributed to consumers who visited the pharmacy during the last six months, with a total population of 48,359 people. Sampling was carried out randomly, with a minimum of 30 samples and a maximum of 500 samples. The number of samples in this study was 248 people. The analysis methods used were validity, reliability, classical assumptions, hypothesis testing and multiple linear regression analysis using the SPSS version 27 application. Based on the test results, it can be concluded that product completeness, outlet atmosphere, service quality, and price perception simultaneously and partially have a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions at Kimia Farma Sam Ratulangi Manado Pharmacy.

Keywords: Product Completeness, Outlet Atmosphere, Service Quality, Price Perception, Purchasing Decision, Kimia Farma Pharmacy

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Introduction

Kimia Farma has been a pillar in providing the best health products and services to the people of Indonesia for more than two centuries. With an extensive network, through PT. Kimia Farma Apotek (KFA), the company operates more than 1,232 pharmacies throughout Indonesia including in the city of Manado. With its strategic position, KFA Sam Ratulangi is also a major indicator of Kimia Farma's success not only in Manado but also nationally. If KFA Sam Ratulangi experiences a decline in service quality, especially a decline in sales transactions, this will certainly have a significant impact on Kimia Farma's reputation and performance as a whole.

KFA Sam Ratulangi Manado, recorded a significant decline in sales over the past three years. In 2022, total sales transactions were 133,934. This number decreased to 118,013 in 2023, and until mid-June 2024, total transactions only reached 48,359. This sharp decline is a serious issue because it can affect business sustainability and the ability of pharmacies to continue to provide optimal health services to the community. Several factors that are suspected of contributing to this decline in sales include a decrease in purchasing decisions for products.

Tan et al. (2020) stated that the completeness of products in pharmacies significantly influences purchasing decisions, because customers tend to choose pharmacies that provide a variety of products to meet all their health needs in one place. On the other hand, Hazizah et al. (2022), in their research revealed the opposite, that the completeness of products does not affect purchasing decisions. Nguyen et al. (2020) revealed that a comfortable and aesthetic outlet atmosphere greatly influences customer comfort, with clean and neatly arranged pharmacies tending to attract more customers. In contrast to the research of Badarudin et al. (2021), it was found that the store atmosphere did not affect purchasing decisions. Clark et al. (2019) emphasized that the quality of service provided by pharmacies, such as staff expertise, friendliness, and speed of service, have a major impact on customer purchasing decisions. Research by Agu et al. (2020) also supports this by emphasizing that the dimensions of service quality, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, and physical evidence, all have a significant effect on consumer purchasing decisions at pharmacies.

Price perception plays an important role in purchasing decisions. The description of several customers of Kimia Farma Samrat Pharmacy shows that the prices of several products at the pharmacy are considered more expensive compared to other pharmacies. According to Ilyas et al. (2022), setting prices that are too high is a problem because most companies fail when the prices set are not in accordance with market affordability. Li et al. (2021) showed that price perception has a significant influence on customer purchasing decisions, where competitive and reasonable prices increase purchase intentions. Meanwhile, prices that are considered higher compared to other pharmacies can encourage customers to look for more affordable alternatives, negatively affecting their purchasing decisions. In contrast, Arnipianti (2021) found that price had no effect

on purchasing decisions.

By analyzing these factors, Kimia Farma Pharmacy can develop more effective strategies to improve sales performance and customer satisfaction at KFA Sam Ratulangi. Based on the background above, and considering the importance of this research for KFA Sam Ratulangi's marketing management policy in increasing sales volume, a study was conducted on "The Influence of Product Completeness, Outlet Atmosphere, Service Quality and Price Perception on Purchasing Decisions at Kimia Farma Sam Ratulangi Manado Pharmacy".

Research purposes

1. Analyzing the influence of product completeness, outlet atmosphere, service quality and price perception simultaneously on purchasing decisions at Kimia Farma Sam Ratulangi Manado Pharmacy
2. Analyzing the influence of product completeness partially on purchasing decisions at Kimia Farma Sam Ratulangi Manado Pharmacy
3. Analyzing the influence of outlet atmosphere partially on purchasing decisions at the Kimia Farma Sam Ratulangi Manado Pharmacy
4. Analyzing the influence of service quality partially on purchasing decisions at Kimia Farma Sam Ratulangi Manado Pharmacy
5. Analyzing the influence of price perception partially on purchasing decisions at Kimia Farma Sam Ratulangi Manado Pharmacy

Literature Review

Marketing Management

According to the American Marketing Association, marketing management is the activity, set of institutions, and processes for creating, communicating, delivering, and exchanging offerings that have value for customers, clients, partners, and society at large. This definition emphasizes the importance of exchange in marketing and managing ongoing relationships with customers. Marketing management is not only focused on selling products or services, but also on building and maintaining long-term, mutually beneficial relationships between companies and customers, including efforts to understand customer needs and wants, and provide relevant and high-value solutions for them (Yulianto et al., 2024). According to Suprpto & Azizi (2020), marketing management includes activities that involve planning, directing, and monitoring in the marketing field. These activities include actions such as recruiting, selecting, planning routes, providing equipment, arranging payments, and motivating the sales team. Marketing management aims to ensure that all aspects of marketing operations run effectively and efficiently.

Based on the understanding of the experts above, it can be concluded that marketing management is an activity that includes selling and offering products or services to meet consumer needs through interactions that build long-term relationships.

Marketing Mix

Musfar (2020) explains that the marketing mix is a tool that is under the control of the company and is used to influence the target market. By controlling and managing these four variables, companies can design effective marketing strategies to attract and retain customers. There are four variables in the marketing mix activity for products, namely:

1. **Product:** Companies make or produce goods to meet customer needs and wants.
2. **Price:** Customers have to pay a certain amount of money to get the product they want. Price is an important component in the marketing mix because it determines the company's profit and survival.
3. **Place:** Companies distribute products in places that are easily accessible to buyers, making placement or distribution an important part of the marketing mix.
4. **Promotion:** Companies use promotions to increase sales by communicating product benefits and persuading target customers to buy the products offered..

Buying decision

According to Dopo & Sagir (2024), purchasing decisions are a series of processes that consumers go through when making transactions with companies. Consumers go through this process to ensure they choose the right object, be it a physical product or a service they need. According to Setyaningsih & Suprpto (2021), purchasing decisions are a stage that occurs after the intention or desire to buy arises. Purchasing decisions occur when the intention or interest to buy has been formed.

Based on the understanding of the experts above, the author concludes that the purchase decision is a complex process that consumers go through after forming an intention or desire to buy a product or service. This process involves the stages of collecting information, evaluating various available alternatives, and finally choosing a product or service that is considered most appropriate to the needs and preferences.

Purchase Decision Indicators

According to Lensun et al. (2020), there are four indicators of purchasing decisions, namely; According to wishes, Determination to buy, Liking the brand, and Recommendations from others.

Product Completeness

In a study by Puspika & Sitorus (2023), it is explained that product completeness refers to the availability of various types of products offered by the company and desired by consumers. According to Kurniawan et al. (2020), product completeness includes aspects of depth, breadth, and quality of product offerings available on the market. Adequate product availability not only meets consumer needs but can also increase their interest in making purchases.

Product Completeness Indicator

Product completeness indicators, as explained by Marina (2024); Diversity of goods sold

in the market, Variation of products sold, Availability of products sold, and Types of brands available.

Outlet Atmosphere

According to Tansala et al. (2019), store atmosphere includes the atmosphere related to the physical characteristics of the exterior and interior spaces of a building, which forms the image of the building and attracts customers. Consumers can assess a store before making a purchase because an attractive store atmosphere can influence their decision to buy a product. Tanjung (2020) explains that store atmosphere is one of the factors in the retail mix that must be considered by retail businesses, such as layout and atmosphere.. According to Farikha et al. (2023), store atmosphere is one of the most important factors in attracting consumers. This atmosphere includes various elements, such as physical layout, lighting, music, aroma, and the overall visual appearance in the store.

From the several definitions above, it can be concluded that the store atmosphere is an important element that includes various physical aspects of the exterior and interior space of a building. Store atmosphere plays a role in shaping the image of the store and attracting customers, thus influencing consumer purchasing decisions.

Outlet Mood Indicator

According to Pratiwi & Yasa (2019), the outlet atmosphere has indicators including: Cleanliness, Layout, Music, Lighting, and Temperature.

Quality of Service

According to Indrasari (2019:61), service quality refers to the performance given by one person to another. This performance can be an intangible action and does not result in ownership of any goods by any party. Service quality depends on the ability to meet customer needs and desires; providing good service is the main key. The significance of service quality is very large for companies because it has a direct impact on customer satisfaction levels (Lestari & Novitaningtyas, 2021).

Based on the definition above, it can be concluded that service quality has great significance in the business context, especially in influencing customer satisfaction. The main key to service quality is the ability to effectively meet consumer needs and desires through various beneficial actions, even though it does not result in ownership of physical goods. This shows that focusing on good service not only increases customer satisfaction, but can also be an important strategy in increasing product variety and guiding more effective policies in business management..

Service Quality Indicators

According to Budiono et al. (2023), the indicators of service quality are as follows: Physical evidence, Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance, and Empathy.

Price Perception

Kotler & Armstrong (2021) highlighted that price is not just a cost paid by consumers, but also reflects the value given in the exchange between consumers and sellers. This implies that price is not only a determinant of costs, but also an indicator of the value of

a product or service that influences consumer perceptions of its quality and relevance to their needs. Depending on the goals the company wants to achieve, each company has a different policy for setting prices. However, the most attractive factor for customers when they choose to buy an item is its price (Hakim et al., 2019). According to Kotler and Keller (2020), price perception is an emotional and rational evaluation of consumers regarding the fairness of the price offered by the seller, as well as its comparison with competitors' prices. Purchasing decisions are often influenced by the extent to which consumers feel the price they pay is commensurate with the benefits or satisfaction they get from the product.

Based on the explanations of several experts above, it is concluded that price in the marketing mix has a very important role in generating company revenue, unlike other elements that require large investments. Consumer perception of price plays a key role in purchasing decisions, where price is seen not only as a cost but also as a value exchanged for the benefits obtained.

Price Perception Indicator

The following are price perception indicators according to Asshiddieqi & Mudiantono (2021): Price affordability, Price competitiveness, Price according to quality, and Price according to benefits.

Previous Research

The Last Supper (2020) in his study entitled Analysis of factors influencing consumer preferences for generic drug purchasing decisions (a study of consumers at the Kimia Farma Pandanaran pharmacy in Semarang City) revealed that service quality and price perceptions influence consumer preferences in purchasing generic drugs at the Kimia Farma Pandanaran Pharmacy in Semarang. Hasugian, Sihombing and Manali (2024) in this study entitled The Influence of Service Quality and Location on Purchasing Decisions at the Otty Rantauprapat Pharmacy revealed that service quality influences purchasing decisions. Nggagho, Kurniawan & Tonce (2024), in this study entitled The Influence of Service Quality and Product Completeness on Purchasing Decisions at the Winola Medika Maumere Pharmacy revealed that service quality has a significant effect on purchasing decisions, as does the variable of product completeness. Sari & Dermawan (2023), in this study entitled The Influence of Store Atmosphere and Product Completeness on Purchasing Decisions at the National Kitchen Store in Kupang City revealed that store atmosphere and product completeness have a positive effect on purchasing decisions.

Research Model

Figure 1.

Research Model

Information: Partial; Simultaneous

Hypothesis

H1: It is suspected that there is a simultaneous influence between Product Completeness, Outlet Atmosphere, Service Quality, and Price Perception on Purchasing Decisions at Kimia Farma Sam Ratulangi Manado Pharmacy.

H2: It is suspected that there is a partial influence of Product Completeness on Purchasing Decisions at the Kimia Farma Sam Ratulangi Manado Pharmacy.

H3: It is suspected that there is a partial influence of Outlet Atmosphere on Purchasing Decisions at the Kimia Farma Sam Ratulangi Manado Pharmacy.

H4: It is suspected that there is a partial influence of service quality on purchasing decisions at the Kimia Farma Sam Ratulangi Manado Pharmacy.

H5: It is suspected that there is a partial influence of Price Perception on Purchasing Decisions at the Kimia Farma Sam Ratulangi Manado Pharmacy

Methodology

This study uses quantitative methods to describe existing phenomena without comparing or connecting independent variables with other variables (Sugiyono, 2019). In this study, the sampling technique was carried out randomly, and data was collected using appropriate instruments. The quantitative data collected were then used to test the established hypotheses, with the results presented without further analysis of the relationship with other variables or certain treatments.

Research Object and Time

This research was conducted at Kimia Farma Sam Ratulangi Manado Pharmacy. This research was conducted from September to October 2024.

Method of collecting data

The data collection technique used by researchers in this study is through a questionnaire to obtain data relevant to organizational problems. The data used is primary data, namely raw data collected directly by researchers from primary sources using questionnaires, where researchers provide written statements to respondents regarding purchasing decisions, product completeness, outlet atmosphere, service quality, and price perception.

Population and Research Sample

According to Sugiyono (2019), population is a generalization area consisting of objects/subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics that are determined to be studied and then conclusions are drawn. The population in this study were consumers who made transactions at Kimia Farma Apotek Sam Ratulangi Manado in the last six months, totaling 48,359 people. The number of samples in this study was 248 respondents, meeting the requirements of a minimum of 30 and a maximum of 500 samples studied in the research period (Amin et al., 2023).

Research Instrument Scale

According to Sugiyono (2019), the Likert scale is used to measure attitudes, opinions, and perceptions of individuals or groups regarding social phenomena. In this study, the Likert scale ranges from 1-5, which includes respondents' answers in five categories, namely strongly agree (5), Agree (4) Undecided (3), Disagree (2) and Strongly Disagree (1).

Data Analysis Methods

After the data was collected, the researcher conducted a statistical data analysis using the SPSS version 27 program which included research instrument testing, classical assumption testing, multiple linear regression testing and hypothesis testing. After conducting data analysis, the results of the data analysis will then be described in the research results.

Validity Test

Ghozali (2021) said that validity is a test carried out to assess the extent of the validity of the questionnaire used. Validity testing is carried out to determine the feasibility of the questions that have been determined in defining the variables. The validity testing criteria according to Sugiyono (2019) state that if $r_{count} > r_{table}$ with a significance level < 0.05 and $df = n - 2$, then the measuring instrument is declared valid and vice versa.

Reliability Test

Reliability is measured by researchers to ensure that the questionnaire used as a variable indicator produces consistent answers over time (Ghozali, 2021). A questionnaire is considered reliable if the Cronbach Alpha Coefficient value is between 0.6 and 1.0.

Normality Test

According to Ghozali (2020), the normality test is used to test whether the independent and dependent variables in the regression model have a normal distribution or not. Data normality testing can be done using the One Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, with the provision that if the significance value is above 5% or 0.05 then the data has a normal distribution. Conversely, if the results of the One Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test show a significance value below 5% or 0.05 then the data does not have a normal distribution. In addition, normality can be seen in the histogram and PP Plot in the SPSS analysis results.

Multicollinearity Test

According to Ghozali (2020), multicollinearity testing aims to determine whether there is a correlation between independent variables or free variables in the regression model. To determine the presence of multicollinearity in the regression model, researchers can look at the tolerance and variance inflation factor (VIF) values. The test results are said to be free from multicollinearity symptoms if the tolerance value is more than 0.10 and the VIF is less than 10.

Heteroscedasticity Test

This test is used to check whether there is a difference in residual variance in each observation in the regression model. If the variance is different, this condition is called heteroscedasticity. If there is no particular pattern and the data is randomly distributed around zero on the y-axis, then it can be concluded that there is no heteroscedasticity. A good research model is a model that is free from heteroscedasticity (Ghozali, 2020).

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Multiple linear regression analysis is useful for determining the influence or direct relationship between two or more independent variables and one dependent variable (Ghozali, 2021).

Coefficient of Determination (R²)

The correlation coefficient (r) analysis aims to determine how close the relationship is between the independent variables and the dependent variable (Sugiyono, 2019). According to Ghozali (2020), the coefficient of determination (R²) is used to measure the extent to which the model is able to explain the variation of the dependent variable. The value of the coefficient of determination ranges between zero and one. If the R² value is small, then the ability of the independent variables to explain the variation of the dependent variable is very limited.

Simultaneous Significance Test (F Test)

According to Sugiyono (2019), the F test aims to determine the influence of independent variables simultaneously (Sugiyono, 2019). The basis for the decision is as follows: H_0 is accepted if $F_{count} < F_{table}$ at a significance level of 5%. H_a is accepted if $F_{count} > F_{table}$ at a significance level of less than 5%.

Partial Significance Test (T-Test)

The t-statistic test is used to test the partial regression coefficient of the independent variable. In the t-test using the formula $df = nk$. The df formula according to Ghozali (2020) is ($df = nk$ where n is the number of samples and k is the number of variables, both independent and dependent variables). If the calculated T value is greater than the T table and the significance value is less than 0.05, then it can be said that the independent variable has a partial effect on the dependent variable, and vice versa.

Operational Definition of Variables and Indicators

1. Purchase Decision, purchase decision is a series of processes that consumers go through when making transactions with a company. Indicators: according to desire, determination to buy, liking the brand and recommendations from others

2. Product Completeness, product completeness refers to the availability of various types of products offered by the company and desired by consumers. Indicators: diversity of goods sold, variety of products sold, types of brands available, and availability of products sold.

3. Outlet atmosphere, includes the atmosphere related to the physical characteristics of the exterior and interior spaces of a building, which shape the image of the building and attract customers. Indicators: cleanliness, layout, music, lighting and temperature.

4. Service quality, service quality refers to the performance that one person provides to another. Indicators: physical evidence, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy.

5. Price Perception, price perception is an emotional and rational evaluation of consumers towards the fairness of the price offered by the seller, as well as its comparison with competitors' prices. Indicators: price affordability, price competitiveness, price according to quality and price according to benefits.

Results and Discussion

Validity Test Results

The results of the validity testing of the research instrument using Statistical Product Service Solution (SPSS) for Windows are summarized in Table 1 below:

Table1. Instrument Validity Test Results

Variables	Indicator	<i>r Count</i>	<i>r Table</i>	Sig	Alpha	Status
Purchase Decision (Y)	Y_1	0.764	0.1246	0.000	0.05	Valid
	Y_2	0.773	0.1246	0.000	0.05	Valid
	Y_3	0.761	0.1246	0.000	0.05	Valid
	Y_4	0.755	0.1246	0.000	0.05	Valid
	Y_5	0.746	0.1246	0.000	0.05	Valid
	Y_6	0.760	0.1246	0.000	0.05	Valid
	Y_7	0.681	0.1246	0.000	0.05	Valid
	Y_8	0.736	0.1246	0.000	0.05	Valid
Product Completeness (X1)	X1_1	0.839	0.1246	0.000	0.05	Valid
	X1_2	0.873	0.1246	0.000	0.05	Valid
	X1_3	0.878	0.1246	0.000	0.05	Valid
	X1_4	0.877	0.1246	0.000	0.05	Valid
	X1_5	0.780	0.1246	0.000	0.05	Valid
	X1_6	0.810	0.1246	0.000	0.05	Valid
Outlet Atmosphere (X2)	X2_1	0.783	0.1246	0.000	0.05	Valid
	X2_2	0.812	0.1246	0.000	0.05	Valid
	X2_3	0.792	0.1246	0.000	0.05	Valid
	X2_4	0.799	0.1246	0.000	0.05	Valid
	X2_5	0.825	0.1246	0.000	0.05	Valid
	X2_6	0.825	0.1246	0.000	0.05	Valid
	X2_7	0.801	0.1246	0.000	0.05	Valid
Service quality (X3)	X3_1	0.868	0.1246	0.000	0.05	Valid
	X3_2	0.900	0.1246	0.000	0.05	Valid
	X3_3	0.826	0.1246	0.000	0.05	Valid
	X3_4	0.869	0.1246	0.000	0.05	Valid
	X3_5	0.904	0.1246	0.000	0.05	Valid
Price Perception (X4)	X4_1	0.880	0.1246	0.000	0.05	Valid
	X4_2	0.914	0.1246	0.000	0.05	Valid

	X4_3	0.875	0.1246	0.000	0.05	Valid
	X4_4	0.842	0.1246	0.000	0.05	Valid

Source: Data processed by SPSS 27 (2024)

Based on Table 1, the results of the questionnaire validity test on 248 respondents are explained as follows:

1. The Purchase Decision Variable (Y) from 8 statement items (Y1-Y8) obtained the lowest correlation value in item Y7 = 0.681 with a significance value = 0.000.
2. The Product Completeness variable (X1) from 6 statement items (X1.1 – X1.6) obtained the lowest correlation value in item X1.5 = 0.780 with a significance value = 0.000.
3. Outlet Atmosphere Variable (X2) from 7 statement items (X2.1 – X2.7) obtained the lowest correlation value in item X2.1 = 0.783 with a significance value = 0.000.
4. Service quality (X3) from 5 question items (X3.1 – X3.5) obtained the lowest correlation value in item X3.3 = 0.826 with a significance value = 0.000.
5. The Price Perception Variable (X4) from 4 question items (X4.1 – X4.4) obtained the lowest correlation value in item X4.4 = 0.842 with a significance value = 0.000.

Based on these results, it can be concluded that all question items from each variable in the questionnaire are valid because the correlation value is > 0.1246 in the r table and n 248 and also the significance value is < 0.05.

Reliability Test Results

The results of reliability testing of all variable items are shown in Table 2 below:

Table2. Reliability Test Results

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha	Standard	Information
Purchase Decision (Y)	0.881	0.60	Reliable
Product Completeness (X1)	0.916	0.60	Reliable
Outlet Atmosphere (X2)	0.907	0.60	Reliable
Service quality (X3)	0.923	0.60	Reliable
Price Perception (X4)	0.897	0.60	Reliable

Source: Data processed by SPSS 27 (2024)

Based on the results of the reliability test in table 2, all instrument items have a Cronbach's Alpha value of more than 0.6, which indicates that all items are reliable. Therefore, all statements in the questionnaire are reliable and can be used for research.

Normality Test Results

The test results using the One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test in Table 3 are as follows:

Table3. One-Sample Kolmogorov Smirnov Test Results

		Unstandardized Residual
N		248
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	.0000000
	Std. Deviation	1.62482991
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.050
	Positive	.050
	Negative	-.050
Test Statistics		.050
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.200
a. Test distribution is Normal.		
b. Calculated from data.		
c. Lilliefors Significance Correction.		

Source: SPSS 27 Data Processing (2024)

In this study, the significance value (sig) obtained was 0.200, which is greater than 0.05, so it can be concluded that the frequency distribution comes from a normally distributed population.

Multicollinearity Test Results

The following is a table of multicollinearity test results:

Table 4 Multicollinearity Test Results

Model		Collinearity Statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)		
	Product Completeness (X1)	0.356	2,811
	Outlet Atmosphere (X2)	0.266	3,761
	Service quality (X3)	0.262	3.815
	Price Perception (X4)	0.397	2,521

a. Dependent Variable: Purchase Decision (Y)

Source: SPSS 27 Data Processing (2024)

Table 4 shows that the VIF value is <10, and the Tolerance value is >0.1, so it can be concluded that there is no multicollinearity phenomenon.

Heteroscedasticity Test Results

According to Ghozali (2021), heteroscedasticity does not occur if the scatterplot image does not show a clear pattern, such as waves, widening, or narrowing, and the points are spread above and below the number 0 on the Y axis. The results of the heteroscedasticity test in this study can be seen in the image below:

Figure 2. Scatterplot Results of Heteroscedasticity Test

Source: SPSS 27 Data Processing (2024)

The results of the heteroscedasticity test show that in the scatterplot with regression standardized predicted value, there is no clear pattern, and the points are spread above and below the number 0 on the Y axis. This indicates that the data in this study is free from heteroscedasticity problems.

F-Test Results (Simultaneous)

The results of the simultaneous F-test analysis can be seen in the table below:

Table5F Test Results

ANOVA						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	3314.705	4	828,676	308,801	.000b
	Residual	652,098	243	2,684		
	Total	3966.802	247			
a. Dependent Variable: Y						
b. Predictors: (Constant), X4,X3, X1, X2; Table F value (Excel): 2.41; Sig Value: 0.05						

Source: Data processed by SPSS 27 (2024)

Based on the test results in Table 5 above, it can be seen that the F count value is 308,801 with the F table value of 2.41 so that the F count value > F table or 308,801 > 2.41 and a significance level of 0.000 < 0.05, it can be concluded that the variables Product Completeness (X1), Outlet Atmosphere (X2), Service Quality (X3), and Price Perception (X4) simultaneously influence purchasing decisions (Y), so Hypothesis H1 can be accepted.

t-Test Results (Partial)

The t-test (partial) was conducted to test the significance of the regression coefficient of the independent variables, which can be seen in the table below:

Table6T-Test Results

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	3,074	0.929		3.309	0.001
	Product_Completeness	0.488	0.052	0.407	9,334	0.000
	Outlet Atmosphere	0.261	0.053	0.246	4,882	0.000
	Quality_of_Service	0.342	0.077	0.227	4.470	0.000
	Price_Perception	0.185	0.060	0.128	3,098	0.002
a. Dependent Variable: Purchase Decision; T Table Value (Excel): 1.97; Sig Value: 0.05						

Source: Data processed by SPSS 27 (2024)

From table 6 above, it can be concluded as follows:

1. The t-value for Product Completeness (X1) is 9.334, which is greater than the t-table of 1.97. With a significance value (sig) of 0.000, which is smaller than 0.05, it can be concluded that H2 is accepted. This shows that there is a positive and significant influence of Product Completeness (X1) on Purchasing Decisions (Y) at Kimia Farma Pharmacy.
2. The t-value for Outlet Atmosphere (X2) is 4.882, which is also greater than the t-table of 1.97. With a significance value (sig) of 0.000, which is smaller than 0.05, so H3 is accepted. This indicates that Outlet Atmosphere (X2) has a positive and significant influence on Purchasing Decisions (Y).
3. The t-value for Service Quality (X3) was recorded at 4.470, exceeding the t-table of 1.97. The significance value (sig) obtained was 0.000, which is smaller than 0.05, so H4 is accepted. This means that there is a positive and significant influence of Service Quality (X3) on Purchasing Decisions (Y).
4. the t-count value is 3.098, higher than the t-table of 1.97. The significance value (sig) is 0.002, which is also smaller than 0.05, so H5 is accepted. This shows that Price Perception (X4) has a positive and significant influence on Purchasing Decisions (Y).

Correlation Coefficient (R) and Determination Coefficient (R2)

The correlation coefficient and determination coefficient values in this research model can be seen in the model summary in the table below:

Table7. Correlation and Determination Coefficient Test Results

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.914 ^a	.836	.833	1,638
a. Predictors: (Constant), Price_Perception, Product_Completeness, Outlet_Atmosphere, Service_Quality				
b. Dependent Variable: Purchase_Decision				

Source: Data processed by SPSS 27 (2024)

In the model summary, it can be seen that the correlation coefficient (R) produced in model 1 is 0.914. which shows that the relationship between these variables and the Purchasing Decision at Kimia Farma Sam Ratulangi Manado Pharmacy reaches 91.4%. This value shows that there is a very strong positive relationship between the variables and the dependent variable. The R Square (R²) value is 0.836. This value shows that 83.6% of the variation in purchasing decisions (Y) can be explained by the independent variables (X1, X2, X3, and X4) used in the model. The remaining 16.4% can be explained by other factors not included in the analysis model in this study. The Adjusted R Square result is 0.833, so it can be interpreted that around 83.3% of the variation in purchasing decisions (Y) can be explained by product completeness (X1), outlet atmosphere (X2), service quality (X3), and price perception (X4) simultaneously.

The Influence of Product Completeness on Purchasing Decisions

The results of multiple linear regression analysis show that product completeness directly affects purchasing decisions at Kimia Farma Sam Ratulangi Manado Pharmacy. Research shows that when consumers are satisfied with the choices available, they are more likely to make larger purchases. The availability of complete products also reflects the pharmacy's ability to follow market trends and demands, thereby improving the pharmacy's image and competitiveness. This study is in line with the findings of Salsabila et al. (2024), Wati (2023) and Nggagho & Tonce (2024), which state that product completeness has a positive and significant impact on consumer purchasing decisions.

The Influence of Outlet Atmosphere on Purchasing Decisions

The results of multiple linear regression analysis show that the outlet atmosphere at Kimia Farma Sam Ratulangi Manado Pharmacy has a significant impact on consumer purchasing decisions. When consumers enter the pharmacy, a comfortable and attractive atmosphere can improve their mood and encourage them to linger and explore the available products. An attractive interior design not only shows professionalism but also provides a sense of security and comfort for customers. When the outlet atmosphere is well designed, consumers are more likely to feel involved and satisfied, which ultimately increases their likelihood of making a purchase. The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Romzy et al. (2023), Wati (2023) and Sari & Dermawan (2023), which states that the store atmosphere has a positive and significant influence on purchasing decisions.

The Influence of Service Quality on Purchasing Decisions

Based on the results of the hypothesis testing that has been carried out, it shows that service quality has a positive and significant influence on purchasing decisions. When customers feel valued and receive fast, efficient service, they are more likely to be

satisfied and make repeat purchases. Well-trained staff with in-depth product knowledge can provide helpful information, increasing consumer confidence in the pharmacy. The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Nggagho & Tonce (2024), Rochmah & Lestari (2024), Yazid & Hidayat (2020), Bayu et al. (2024) and Hasugian, et al. (2024) who found that service quality partially and simultaneously influences purchasing decisions made by consumers.

The Influence of Price Perceptions on Purchasing Decisions

This study found that there is a positive influence between price perception and purchasing decisions. Competitive pricing, especially for frequently sought-after products, can attract more customers. In addition, the right discount or promotion strategy can increase the appeal of prices and encourage impulsive buying decisions. The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Li et al. (2021) and Kamilah & Khasanah (2022), which found that price perception has a positive and significant influence on purchasing decisions

Conclusions

1. Product completeness, outlet atmosphere, service quality and price perception have a positive and significant influence simultaneously on purchasing decisions at Kimia Farma Sam Ratulangi Manado Pharmacy.
2. Product completeness has a positive and significant partial effect on purchasing decisions at the Kimia Farma Sam Ratulangi Manado Pharmacy.
3. Outlet atmosphere has a positive and significant partial influence on purchasing decisions at Kimia Farma Sam Ratulangi Manado Pharmacy
4. Service quality has a positive and significant partial effect on purchasing decisions at Kimia Farma Sam Ratulangi Manado Pharmacy
5. Price perception has a positive and significant partial effect on purchasing decisions at Kimia Farma Sam Ratulangi Manado Pharmacy.

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